

Med-drone

Project Management Plan

Project Management Plan

Project Name	Med-drone	Project Number	01
Customer	Ignite-NIC	Prepared By	Project Manager

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Document Change History

Created by:		Project Manager	Created on Date:		1st November 2022
Change Date	Changed by	Reason Description	Comment	Approver	
1.0 (10/11/22)	Project Manager	To complete the project overview section		Project Manager & Com. Manager	
2.0 (10/11/12)	Project Manager	Identified the opportunity drivers of the project		Project Manager & Product Manager	
3.0 (10/11/22)	Project Manager	Defined the methodology of the project		Project Manager & Product Manager	
4.0 (11/11/22)	Product Manager	Created the project scope management plan		Project Manager	
5.0 (11/11/22)	Finance Manager	Formed the project cost management plan		Project Manager	
6.0 (11/11/22)	Communication Manager	Created project communication management plan & responsibility assignment matrix		Project Manager & Product Manager	
7.0 (12/11/22)	Communication Manager	Formed project human resource management plan		Project Manager & Product Manager	
8.0 (12/11/2)	Scheduling & Operations Manager	Formed project time management plan		Project Manager & Product Manager	
9.0 (12/11/22)	Risk Assessment Manager	To identify the potential risks and obstacles for our project.		Project Manager & Finance Manager	

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1.0 Project Overview

The current economic conditions and doubled fuel prices have almost made it inevitable to run day-to-day errands even at a shorter distance. Consumers have expressed a need for convenient and cost-effective service for their basic chores such as grocery shopping, food takeaways, and much more. Technology integration has made it easier to come up with such solutions. To serve and cater to the needs of this segment, we have come up with a service called 'Med-drone'. Med-drone is a mobile application through which customers can place orders for their regular medicines to the nearest pharmacy which can be delivered via drone within a few minutes at a reasonable cost. This service will also focus on other segments such as pensioners who have to renew their monthly prescriptions and collect medicines from their panel pharmacies or hospitals.

The estimated start-up cost for this project is PKR 2,280,000 whereas the operational cost would be PKR 1,720,000. We aim to complete this project within the span of 20 months with the following plan:

- Research: 2 months
- Planning: 8 months
- Design and Development: 5 months
- Pilot Testing: 2 months
- Marketing and Launch: 3 months

Through this project we plan to reduce the time between order placement and fulfillment (lead time) for our customers. The limited time and resource use in this service would save the fuel costs for our customers as they would only have to pay a small number of delivery charges in addition to their purchase. Reduced fuel usage also translates into fewer contributions to the carbon footprint in the twin cities. Since our target segment mostly consists of older and middle-aged people, we intend to provide a user-friendly interface via our mobile application for the convenience of customers.

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2.0 Opportunity Drivers

This section should contain a check next to the drivers that have initiated this opportunity.

New Customer <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	New Technology <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Joint Venture <input type="checkbox"/>	Business Need <input type="checkbox"/>
Existing Customer Request <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Market Demand <input type="checkbox"/>	Legal Requirement <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/>

3.0 Project Methodology

The main methodology that our project is based on is the Agile Methodology. This methodology works on breaking the project into several phases to manage and complete it. Constant involvement of stakeholders is crucial to the success of a project under this methodology. An agile methodology starts with identifying the problems of consumers and documenting a vision statement for it. Several teams are required to work on such a project with constant collaboration. The start of an agile approach is always by keeping the customer (user) in mind. User personas are defined to create the workflow roles by understanding various customer groups and their behavior.

The agile methodology also helps in reducing the costs, time, and provides flexibility for changes in terms of improvement. Moreover, to obtain any feedback regarding the project, the team members can track the development of the project alongside instead of waiting for the testing. As the steps are visible to all the parties involved, this gives a sense of control to them using agile approach. For this methodology some of the tools that will be used as following:

Microsoft Project is a project management software designed and sold by the Microsoft. It is used by a project manager in developing a schedule regarding the activities of a project while maintaining the budget and the workload. We will use Ms Project to design our work breakdown structure and resource management.

Microsoft Outlook is an information management tool that is used to collaboration and communication among teams. The primary mode of communication is this software is email but managing a calendar is also a function. Other functions include note taking, journal logging, task management.

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Microsoft Power BI is a business intelligence software that helps in connecting data to form linearity, visualization, and interactive comprehension. It can be used to track the performance of the project by measuring the key performance indicators.

Asana: A project management tool that is used by teams for organizing, managing, and tracking their assigned work. Asana is usually proved beneficial for working with smaller teams.

Trello: This software pretty much serves the same purpose as the later with an additional advantage of a mobile interface which makes it beneficial and more convenient for the users. Team members can collaborate from any location at any time as per the requirement.

ProofHub: Also known as the ‘all-in-one’ project software, ProofHub has all the required resources for a project from start till the end. Templates for various project plans and charters can aid as a soft tool in the project and help enhance the process of documentation.

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4.0 Project Scope Management Plan

The project scope management plan explains how the scope of the project would be defined, modified, and monitored throughout the project. It has the following components.

1. Scope Statement

The Following tasks will have to be carried out in order to deliver the project.

- i. Research:* This step will include the identification of key stakeholders and the examination of market dynamics.
- ii. Planning:* This step will include determining the resources required, for example, the number of drones and the type of application needed to deliver the service. Furthermore, planning will include budget and schedule analysis, time and cost required to develop the application and purchase the drones. Lastly, risk analysis will also be carried out in this step.
- iii. Design and Development:* This step will focus on the design and development of the application along with the purchase of drones.
- iv. Pilot testing:* The service as a whole integrated solution will be tested. Drones will be tested for their flight, time, speed, and signal strength test. The application will be tested for its compatibility with drones and its ease of usage.
- v. Market:* In this step, the service will finally be available for the market along with its advertisements on print and social media.

2. Creating Work Breakdown Structure

Phases, activities, and tasks are to be defined for our project along with their durations. Resources will be allocated to the activities. Our project constitutes of 5 phases namely project initiation, project planning, project execution, project implementation, and project closing. These phases are further divided into activities and tasks. Further, the activities will be sequenced and link between these activities will be established. Cost, duration, and resources for all activities will be calculated.

3. Maintenance and approval of scope

Scope will be maintained and monitored throughout the project. This will be done at

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individual task level. The quality of deliverables at each task will be evaluated by quality manager. Duration and cost of each task will also be controlled throughout the project. Project and product manager will oversee the overall progress of the project.

In case the scope will have to be changed or altered, the change management system would be followed by formally submitting the request to the change control Committee which will further review that whether these changes are needed. Once these are approved, the budget and schedule will be changed so that minimum time and cost is involved.

Formal acceptance of project deliverables

The project scope will be approved at three levels that are project manager, product project manager and communication manager. Because project scope is one of the most significant parts that actually defines the entire product in terms of its functionality, hence it requires to be approved from maximum people. Communication manager will be the one coordinating all the activities of the project so he will have a better idea about whether the project scope is being met or not.

5.0 Project Time Management Plan

PROJECT ACTIVITY LIST:

- 1. Project Initiation
- 2. Project Planning
- 3. Project Execution
- 4. Project Controlling
- 5. Project Closing

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Resource Breakdown Structure:

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Project Key Dates

Activity Name	Date	Milestone	Risk	Resource Assigned
Project Initiation	1/02/23 to 1/24/23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Project Planning	1/2/23 to 3/29/23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Facility
Project Execution	3/10/23 to 5/12/23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Software, Staffing and training, Equipment, Advertisement, Licenses
Project Controlling	4/19/23 to 5/16/23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Project Closing	5/16/23 to 6/8/23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Advertisement
		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Please note: all risks must be logged in the Project Risk Register (Log). A Contingency Plan and Fallback Plan should also be noted for each risk specified in the Project Risk Register.

6.0 Project Communication Management Plan

Med drone stakeholder includes employees, suppliers, customers, competitors and government. Software Engineer and Computer Scientist are med drone’s employees. While Qumaq Technologies Pvt. Ltd, Woot Tech Pvt. Ltd, Shaheen Chemist, D. Watson Pharmacy, Shifa Pharmacy are the suppliers. Residents of Twin Cities are med drone’s customers. Furthermore, PandaMart and Cheetay are going to be med drone’s strong competitors. Lastly, Drug Regulatory Authority comes under government.

Devising an effective communication management plan is extremely significant since effective communication guarantees the success of the project and ensures that each of your stakeholders are on the same page and their contributions align with the goals of the project. This is only possible when you use appropriate communication channels and delivers your message in a clear and easy to understand manner.

Employees:

Foremost, Med drone understands the importance of employees and how a significant degree of success and failure is related to their performance. Hence, med drone will make sure that they communicate with their employees on various platforms such as face to face meetings, emails,

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telephone etc. and delivers message with clarity by communicating the project goals, giving them a say in decision making so they feel trusted and contribute effectively. Constant feedback will be provided so that software engineers and computer scientists can make improvements accordingly. It will also help to address any confusions or doubts faced by them which will ultimately raise their morale and performance. They will be given assistance wherever it is required and any change in plan regarding cost, time, and quality will be communicated as soon as possible.

Suppliers:

Med drone will make sure that all the orders for drones and medicines are communicated in a clear and concise manner with the respective suppliers through efficient communication channels and on time so that suppliers get sufficient time to prepare order and deliver it timely. The product and delivery quotations, product quality, quantity, delivery time, delivery channels will be agreed upon by both parties beforehand in order to avoid any misunderstandings in the later phase. This will ensure cordial relationship between med drone and its suppliers.

Customers:

Med drone will ensure that customer's preferences and needs are catered for effectively and all the terms and conditions are communicated properly so that customers are able to base their decisions on the correct information provided to them. Any promotional offers or deals will be communication on numerous platforms such as on official website, other corporate websites, social media platforms, journals, magazines, emails, text messages so that not a single potential customer misses the opportunity. Customers' reservations and feedback regarding the service will be taken as an opportunity to improve our service in the best interests of our valued customers.

Competitors:

Med drone understands the significance of maintaining competitiveness in this competitive era and staying one step ahead of its competitors. For this Med drone will ensure that healthy competition remains but at the same time it captures more market and sales than its competitors in a good manner based on the service of quality and rates it offers to its customers.

Government:

Med drone will ensure that it complies with all the rules and regulations of drug regulatory The Project Management Plan is created in the Planning Process Group. This Plan is a formal document used to manage the execution of the project. The Project Management Plan integrates the outputs of the planning processes including (but not limited to) all of the subsidiary project management plans into this one comprehensive document.

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authority and get the required decisions approved. It will clearly communicate its mission, vision, basic purpose, objectives and the drone's specifications such as the temperature of drone in which medicines are kept and the nature of medicines which med drone delivers will be communicated with the authority so that their concerns and queries get addressed. So, in case of any changes required, med drone can incorporate them timely.

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6.1 Responsibility Assignment Matrix (RAM)

Communication Management Plan Matrix

Communication Management Matrix		
Project Number: 01	Project Name: Med-drone	Project Manager: Ayesha Ahmed Khan

Name	Role	Level of Responsibility
Ayesha Ahmad Khan	Project Manager	In charge of the planning, procurement, implementation and completion of the project.
Arwa Zainab Irfan	Product Manager	In charge of product development, distribution, and promotion during the product life cycle.
Ayesha Laraib	Quality Assurance Manager	In charge of upholding the highest reliability and quality standards throughout the product development and production process.
Hamda Naseer	Communications Manager	In charge of internal and external communication forums that effectively define and market the project and its products.
Hamna Asad	Finance Manager	In charge of the complete financial well-being of the project.
Shahwar Naseer	Operations Manager	In charge of the operational activities at each level of the project.
Zainib Ehsan	Risk Assurance Manager	In charge of communicating risk processes and policies for the project.

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Responsibility Assignment Matrix:

Activity	Managers						
	Ayesha Ahmad Khan	Arwa Zainab Irfan	Ayesha Laraib	Hamda Naseer	Hamna Asad	Shahwar Naseer	Zainib Ehsan
Project Initiation (Research)	R	C	C	C	C	C	C
Project Planning (Project charter, Project approval, Management Plan, Budgeting, Time & cost estimation)	A	C	C	A	R	C	C
Project execution (app development, legal requirements, hiring & training)	R	R	R	A	C	C	R
Project Controlling (Application & drone testing)	A	R	R	A	I	C	R
Project Closing (Advertisement & app availability)	R	R	I	A	I	I	I

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7.0 Project Quality Management Plan

<p>Product definition</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “med-drone” is a system enabling the delivery of medicines through drones in the twin cities. • The drone will be connected to a mobile application. Order will be placed through the application, which will notify the nearest reliable pharmacy to dispatch the order through the drone. • The customer will make an online payment for the purchase. The two components of our service are mobile application and delivery drone. • The application will be called “med-drone” and will be compatible with both IOS and android software. The customers will download the application and make their accounts. • Orders will be placed for the required medicines and would be paid for online. The application will locate the nearest reliable pharmacy and notify the drone to pick up the order from the pharmacy. Pharmacies will also be notified when the order is placed. • Customers will be able to track the drone throughout the delivery. Upon reaching the destination, the application will notify the customers. • The application will have separate accounts for people who have various hospitals on their panels. After every month, the application will allow the customers to digitally renew their prescriptions without having to visit the hospital. This can prove to be beneficial, especially for old people who are not able to travel frequently.
<p>Project goals and objectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce lead time by 3/4th (75%) for customers via drone delivery • Improve software usability to counter the risk of application malfunctions • Cut down delivery costs by 50% for customers by saving fuel costs • Conduct pilot testing of our service after 15 months at Ayub National Park Rawalpindi • Achieve net-zero carbon emissions as a business
<p>Quality statement</p>	<p>“Med drone’s fundamental goal is to gain and sustain the trust of the customers by providing a service that is time efficient and cost effective. Med drone developers and employees have embodied this principle by continuously</p>

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	<p>researching and applying the relevant knowledge about the potential customers, delivery products and suppliers. In order to achieve the highest quality of services at Med drone, following guidelines have been established:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular feedback from customers in order to consistently provide the highest quality of service to them. • Consistent monitoring of the employee performance and providing workforce with weekly reports in order to keep the staff informed about the improvements and lack of it regarding Med drone’s service.”
<p>Quality planning</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The workforce is employed which possesses the appropriate skillset to handle the processes of the business. The evaluation is done through application forms, interviews and training sessions. • Rigorous training sessions for employees and pharmacy owners to ensure the quality of the service. • Weekly feedback from users of the service. • Daily assessment of • Monthly Assessment of how effective Marketing is working in favor of med-drone through feedback forms. • Daily evaluation of technical difficulties by collecting data through customer’s feedback and company’s database.
<p>Outcomes of quality planning</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The company is able to sustain itself due to tapping into a small market first i.e., The twin cities. • Obtain its goal of providing timely and cost-effective solution of medicine delivery for its users.

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8.0 Project Change Control Management Process

In case after pilot testing we realize that the current model requires some changes in terms of improvement in the application interface, incorporation of additional features in application and enhancing safety of drone, we should therefore follow the change management system by formally submitting the request to the change control committee which will further review that whether these changes are needed and are according to the scope. Once these are approved, the budget and schedule will be changed so that minimum time and cost is involved. These changes will be evaluated and if these enhance the service and customer satisfaction then the decision will prove to be successful and useful for the long term. On the contrary, if economic conditions of the country are not favorable, changes have to be made that are beyond the control of the business and hence these will be more difficult to cope and will require extensive change in the scope.

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9.0 Project Cost Management Plan

The objective of this cost management plan is to limit the costs associated with Med-Drone throughout the project. This plan outlines the procedure and requirements for measuring, reporting, and controlling project expenses in order to guarantee that the project is effectively completed within the allowed budget. The project's costs include a variety of outlays. This strategy will include metrics, concerns about cost variance, and reporting activities. All important project participants and stakeholders must follow and support this Cost Management Strategy and the overall project plan in order to successfully execute this project. The financial manager will provide the cost management report on monthly bases and an overall financial report on quarterly bases

Organizational Procedure Links

The project costs will be monitored using the project team's timesheets and the project management cost tracking software. The following fields will be recorded for each piece as the expenses are broken down by work package.

Client > Project > Special Key > Work Package Name > WBS ID > Cost Code >

Control Thresholds

Information on cost-management strategies will be included in the Med-Drone Cost Management Status Report. All cost variances from those criteria in this Cost Management Plan will be reported, along with any proposed counteractive actions. Change requests will be identified and tracked in the monthly status report using project cost overruns. If the project exceeds one of the control thresholds for the Cost Performance Index (CPI) and Schedule Performance Index (SPI), between 0.9 and 1, or if the SPI and CPI, has a variance between 0.2 and 0.3 since the previous reporting period, the Project Manager must notify the Sponsor of the exception. If the CPI and SPI reaches one of the control thresholds of less than 0.9 or greater than 1, or if the SPI and CPI has a variance of greater than 0.3, the Project Manager will report the reason for the exception and provide executive management with a Cost Variance Corrective Action Plan to return the project's The Project Management Plan is created in the Planning Process Group. This Plan is a formal document used to manage the execution of the project. The Project Management Plan integrates the outputs of the planning processes including (but not limited to) all of the subsidiary project management plans into this one comprehensive document.

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performance to acceptable levels. The project manager will present potential solutions to the sponsor within six business days of the cost variance being first reported. After the project sponsor decides on a course of corrective action, the manager will deliver a formal Cost Variance Corrective Action Plan to them within two business days. The Cost Variance Corrective Action Plan outlines the steps necessary to bring the project back under budget as well as how its activities will be evaluated for effectiveness. If the remedial steps to be taken result in a change, the project's overall Change Control Process must be followed. The project schedule will be modified to include the corrective measures after the Cost Variance Corrective Action Plan has been approved. The defined project change request procedure will often be followed by the cost change control process. The Sponsor must give his or her consent before making modifications to a project's budget or costs.

Rules of Performance Management

Utilizing earned value management (EVM), the strategy for analyzing cost performance includes monitoring and controlling project spending. To assist the project management team in evaluating and monitoring the performance and advancement of the project, EVM integrates project scope, cost, and schedule measurements. The following earned value measurements will be looked at by the senior project director and/or project resources: Schedule Variance, Cost Variance, Schedule Performance Index, and Cost Performance Index. CPI or SPI less than 1.0 indicates poorer-than-planned project performance and the project manager must report the reasons.

Cost Reporting and Format

Daily cost inputs will be made in ClickUp. Reporting from the project team will be done via dashboards. They provide a thorough overview of data from various sources and aid in the monitoring, measurement, and analysis of pertinent data in important areas. Costs will be exported from ClickUp and reported weekly to the Project Board and Stakeholders on the Project Status Report. Any deviations from the project tolerance must be notified to the PMO and the appropriate approver.

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Additional Details

- Funding sources include equity capital from the 7 partners and a loan from the bank. Each partner contributes Rs. 150,000 and the remaining is financed through a Rs 3,000,000 loan at 13.75% Interest with Rs 46,130 loan repayments for 10 years.
- Pakistani rupee is the currency used to manage the project.
- Pakistani rupee is currency used for the organization's financial books

Start-Up Costs

Start Up Costs		
Investment Items	Specification	Amount
Company Registration	Partnership Registration Fee and Online Company Incorporation Fee	Rs 30,000
Research & Development	Study the target markets	Rs 150,000
Drones (4)	To deliver medicines	Rs 600,000
Mobile Application	Mobile App to place online orders	Rs 1,500,000
Start Up Costs		Rs 2,280,000

The company will require an initial cost of Rs 2,280,000 to start the business. This start-up capital will include one-time expenses of company registration fee, market research, drone procurement and mobile application development.

Operating Costs

Operation Costs		
Payment Items	Monthly/Quarterly	Amount
Office Rent	Monthly	Rs 150,000
Salaries	Monthly	Rs 1,500,000
Advertising	Monthly	Rs 40,000
Maintenance	Monthly	Rs 30,000
Total Operating Costs		Rs 1,720,000

All operating costs incur on a monthly basis. Office rent will cost Rs, 150,000 per month. Salaries include the fees paid to managers and staff which will total to an expense of Rs. 1,500,000. Advertising expense of Rs. 40,000 will continue to increase in the initial phase of the business. The Drones will require monthly maintenance, which will cost Rs 30,000.

Profitability Analysis

	Initial Investment	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Total Cost	-Rs 2,280,000	Rs 1,790,000	Rs 1,790,000	Rs 1,805,000	Rs 1,807,000	Rs 1,807,000
Total Revenue		Rs 1,980,000	Rs 2,340,000	Rs 2,520,000	Rs 2,700,000	Rs 2,700,000
Total Profit (Loss)	-Rs 2,280,000	Rs 190,000	Rs 550,000	Rs 715,000	Rs 893,000	Rs 893,000
Cumulative		-Rs 300,000	Rs 2,040,000	Rs 4,560,000	Rs 7,260,000	Rs 9,960,000
Cumulative (including cost)		-Rs 2,090,000	-Rs 1,540,000	-Rs 825,000	Rs 68,000	Rs 961,000

According to the return on investment, investing in this business would result in a profit of 1.42%. The payback period predicts that the initial investment will be recovered in 4 years, at which point the business will start to make enough money to cover its costs. The fixed cost is Rs 4778, the variable cost per unit is Rs 82, and the sales price per unit is Rs 100. Therefore, Rs. 265 is the break-even sales figure. Costs and revenues for the business will be equal at this time, and it won't be generating a profit or losing money. Due to income above the break-even point during the last four years, the business is profitable.

10.0 Project Human Resource Management Plan

The Project Human Resource Management plan will define roles and responsibilities of all team members for successful project completion. The project manager having the key role will manage and lead the project. The project manager will assign responsibilities to all team members and ensure smooth running of the project. The project manager will also communicate with the stakeholders of the project about the project objectives and requirements. The project manager will create the Project Management Plan in the Planning Process Group. This Plan is a formal document used to manage the execution of the project. The Project Management Plan integrates the outputs of the planning processes including (but not limited to) all of the subsidiary project management plans into this one comprehensive document.

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take part in resolving any conflict that might arise during the project completion between the personnel. The project manager will be expected to make crucial decisions in case of any unexpected conditions and will approve the project deliverables. The project manager will have authority over all team members and will inspire the team to boost their morale. The product manager will be responsible for product development, distribution, and promotion during the product life cycle. Furthermore, finance manager will be in charge of the complete financial well-being of the project including cost, revenue and profitability estimates. The communication manager will be managing internal and external communication forums that effectively define and market the project and its products. Moreover, the operations manager will handle operational activities at each level of the project. The risk assurance manager will communicate all the risks involved in the project and will find for ways to mitigate the risk. The risk assurance manager will communicate with team members and look for risks that might affect the project before and after execution and develop processes and policies to mitigate those risks. A risk analysis will be performed to identify the risks and risk management plan will be prepared by the risk manager. The risk management will be evaluated to monitor the process. Quality Assurance Manager will evaluate the quality of overall project. All the activities and plans will be monitored by quality assurance manager for the approval. Any mistake or defect identified will be communicated by quality assurance manager to the concerned team member. A system of quality and reliability testing will be adopted by quality assurance manager. The quality manager will develop, implement and manage all the processes to ensure that project will meet the required quality standards and specifications. The quality assurance manager will communicate the quality standards to product development team and all other team members. The software engineer will develop the app for medicine order placement and integrate the drone with the app. The software engineer will create and implement the source code. The code will be tested and debug. The computer scientists will work alongside software engineers to create codes and algorithms. The computer scientists will also help integrate the app with the drone technology. The drone pilot will have strong information technology ability to carry out the flights and plan the flight path. The drone technology will be tested by the drone pilot to ensure smooth drone flights on execution.

The three key transition phases for all the team members and manager will be; orientation into The Project Management Plan is created in the Planning Process Group. This Plan is a formal document used to manage the execution of the project. The Project Management Plan integrates the outputs of the planning processes including (but not limited to) all of the subsidiary project management plans into this one comprehensive document.

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project team: Orientation onto the project team, Transition off of the team, and Exit Procedure for closing out personnel-related issues with the employees and functional manager.

During Orientation phase, the team members and manager will be introduced to the project manager and their supervisors. A brief overview of project aim and objectives will be given. A hardcopy of project mission and deliverables will be given. The project organization will be explained along with the timelines of tasks and activities. The employees and managers will be informed about their roles and responsibilities. The members of project will be informed about the hierarchy and their responsibilities to explicitly inform them about who they are required to communicate in a given situation. A supervisor will be assigned to help them adapt in the environment. The rules and regulations of the project work environment will be communicated. They will be informed about the work hours and elapsed hours. The exceptional holidays like Eid and other national holidays will be communicated. The employees will be communicated about the accepted project standards and documented project assumptions. They will be given Project Quality Manual and progress reporting and will be reviewed about standard tools and system. The performance requirement and evaluation criteria of all team members will be communicated. The team will be introduced to the team procedures and the atmosphere. The team leadership, conflict resolution procedure and communication format to be followed will be communicated. During orientation, they will be given a tour of project facility and will be given a functional walk-through to adapt and start working on project. Second phase is transition off of the project team, a plan needs to be prepared in case a project gets delayed or even discontinued and those involved are transitioned to another project or terminated. The process to transition people off involves acknowledging the fact that the person who leave. It can get hard depending upon the reason why the employee left and its consequences on the project. But some human resource policies need to be followed to ensure that everything goes well. The employee contribution and achievements should be acknowledged. Additionally, the other team members and stakeholders will be informed about the departure. The agreement or contract will be closed and the documentation for departure will be signed by the employee. The payments and invoices that are required to be made will be made. Additionally, their access to certain systems and tools will be restricted for security purposes. For reasons of confidentiality, the project document and intellectual property will be

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returned to the project. The tasks and work will be transitioned to other team members to continue the project, or a new employee will be hired if the situation arises. Project management software will help transition people off the project. In case of transition of work process, the outstanding tasks will be finished and communicate the team about new system implementation. The team members will be encouraged to use it, they will be given trainings and feedback to improve their performance. The team members' activities and specialized knowledge will be identified, so as to utilize it in the transition wherever possible. A transition plan will be created with timelines, each candidate's task and status of the project. The plan will be communicated throughout the team to align all team member with the project objectives. Upon successful project or phase completion, the contribution of the project team will be appreciated and they might be helped find new project assignment. The status of project completion will be announced and inform them about the project results. . The changes required in the project will be dealt with professionalism, such as planning change successfully by dividing each task according to the roles of individuals. Exit procedure is extremely significant to practice when required because conflicts are inevitable in a project. Some of the sources of conflicts include finite resources, scheduling priorities, and personal work styles which usually differ among project managers. Some of the factors that strongly impact conflict resolution method includes importance and intensity of the conflict, time pressure for resolving the conflict, relative power of the people involved in the conflict, importance of maintaining cordial relationship, and lastly motivation to resolve conflict on a long-term or short-term basis. Furthermore, there are 5 major techniques to resolve conflicts which we'll implement according to the situation. Withdraw/avoid, Smooth/accommodate, Compromise/reconcile, Force/direct and Collaborate/problem solve. Withdrawing means avoiding or fleeing a potential dispute; delaying action until you are more prepared or until someone else can handle it. While, accommodating means putting more emphasis on points of agreement than those of disagreement; renouncing one's viewpoint in order to accommodate others' wants in order to preserve relationships and harmony. Compromising refers to attempting to find a temporary or partial resolution to the problem by finding solutions that satisfy all sides to some extent. Sometimes using this strategy leads to a lose-lose scenario. Moreover directing means promoting one's ideas at the expense of others; providing only lose-lose solutions, generally while using one's position of authority to solve a problem. This

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strategy frequently produces a win-lose outcome. Lastly, collaborating involves cooperation and open communication to incorporate numerous points of view and insights from many angles, which usually results in agreement and commitment. This strategy may lead to a win-win outcome. So these are the strategies we'll implement in case of serious personnel related issues as they will guarantee success.

The training plan will identify training objectives, schedule and strategy for its implementation. The employees will be evaluated for their skills and capabilities. The current and future needs of their role in the project will be identified during project planning. The gap between needs and human resource capital will be filled by training. During project execution, the members will be monitored to see their progress after training and if they need further training. The training schedule of each team member will be prepared and cost will be estimated during planning. The evaluation criteria to evaluate the training will be defined. Online, on-the-job and computer based training will be provided for technical skills. These types of training are getting common nowadays due to COVID outbreak. These training are less time consuming and will not delay the project. Unplanned training can also be provided to employees based on observation, performance evaluation and conversations. Soft skills and management skills will be polished through mentoring and coaching at the workplace. A few employees might be sent to training institute based on their responsibilities of role and need in the project.

A chart will be used to show the number of employees required in the organization.

Months	Employees	Employee roles (Managers)
January	4	Product Manager+Project Manager+Cost and Scheduling Manager+Quality Assurance Manager
February	6	Product Manager+Project Manager+Cost and Scheduling Manager+ Software Engineer+ Quality Assurance Manager +Finance Manager
March	8	Product Manager+Project Manager+Cost and Scheduling Manager+ 3 Software Engineer+ 2 Computer Scientist
April	8	Product Manager+Project Manager+Cost and Scheduling Manager+ 3 Software Engineer+ 2 Computer Scientist
May	10	Product Manager+Project Manager+Cost and Scheduling Manager+ 3 Software Engineer+ 2 Computer Scientist+Drone Pilots+Risk Assurance Manager
June	8	Product Manager+Project Manager+Cost and Scheduling Manager+ Software Engineer+ Computer Scientist+Drone Pilots+Quality Assurance Manager+ Risk Assurance Manager

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Organizational Chart:

Activate
Go to Sett

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Job Description: Project Manager
Plan and advance the project concept
Assemble and direct the team
Track the status of the project
Set due dates.
Put problems to rest
Money management
Ensure stakeholder happiness
Analyze the performance of the project, including that of the team members
Resolving disputes between team members
Control change

Job Description: Product Manager
Recognizing and expressing user requirements
Market research and creating competitive evaluations
Creating a product's vision
Bringing stakeholders together to support the product's goal
Putting emphasis on a product's strengths and qualities
Fostering a common brain among larger teams to encourage independent judgment

Job Description: Quality Assurance Manager
Creates, implements, and oversees procedures to guarantee, before a product is delivered, that it satisfies the requirements for quality, dependability, and functionality
Identifies and establishes parameters and standards for product quality that are appropriate
Informs the QA team, the product development team, and other necessary workers of the quality standards and criteria
Coordinates the testing of products
Takes part in evaluating products

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11.0 Approval Procedure

Foremost for product description, project product manager will be the person who will approve the description of the product by assuring that all the features, attributes of the product are in alignment with the project objectives and whether it's meeting the requirements of targeted segment. Also, how feasible the product/service is to enter the market and how much business will benefit from it. Secondly, project scope will be approved at three levels that are project manager, product project manager and communication manager. Because project scope is one of the most significant parts that actually defines the entire product in terms of its functionality, hence it requires to be approved from maximum people. Communication manager will be the one coordinating all the activities of the project so he will have a better idea about whether the project scope is being met or not. Thirdly, quality statement and evaluation criteria will be approved by quality assurance manager by evaluating whether the quality is up to the mark through first identifying and then monitoring risks while using techniques such as total quality management, quality control etc. Furthermore, risk identification will be approved by project risk manager and project cost and scheduling manager. They will check if right risks are identified and whether appropriate solutions have been provided to minimize or completely eliminate their probability of occurrence. Moreover, cost and scheduling will be approved by project cost and scheduling manager. He will be the one evaluating all possible costs and how they can be controlled if some of them are in excess.

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12.0 Project Risk Management Plan

Risk Area		Risk Factors	Probability	Impact Rating	Priority	Owner
Functional/Technical		<i>Brief description of the risks</i>	<i>VeryLow/Low/ Moderate/High/Very High</i>	<i>Low/Medium/High</i>	1-10	<i>Identify Personnel</i>
CUSTOMER REQUIREMENT	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Engagement of community is also necessary. Privacy concerns might also arise due to ability of drone to transmit and record data	Moderate	Medium	5	Operation Manager, Project Manager and Deputy Product Manager
PRODUCT REQUIREMENT	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	The autonomous drone might be vulnerable to the risk of being controlled by hackers.	Moderate	Medium	7	Product Manager
RESOURCE REQUIREMENT	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Risk of resource is lack of staff, funding and time. Absence of landing area can be a concern.	Low	High	8	Quality Assurance Manager
TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	If drone is unable to deliver beyond vision then it can threaten our system.	Low	High	7	Product Manager
TIMING	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Project completion takes more time due to unanticipated change in scope.	Low	High	6	Quality Assurance Manager, Cost and Scheduling Manager

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EXTERNAL CONSIDERATION	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delivery drones require licenses from the government for being operated which can be a challenge. Exchange rate of Pakistan is unstable with high fluctuations.	Moderate	Medium	5	Project Manager
FINANCIAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lack of capital needed to purchase the drone, staff to execute the drone technology and IT app.	Low	High	8	Quality Assurance Manager, Finance Manager and Project Manager
INDUSTRY REQUIREMENT	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lack of government regulations regarding drone usage in health sector.	Moderate	Medium	6	Project Manager

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MTC Integration

Risk Mitigation Technique

All the potential risks that can adversely affect the project are identified and addressed in the following risk assessment.

Customer Requirement:

The customer of our project is our project sponsor, a risk that can arise is sponsor does not understand the technology or do not think that its financials profitable. Communication manager will ensure that the project is clearly defined with terms that are understandable by sponsor. The financial risk of this project will be addressed by making financial risk management models that are resilient.

Customer engagement is necessary for our project because it will be the first time in twin cities when drone will deliver medicines to its customers. There is a risk that customers might be reluctant to purchase the drone. To address this risk, extensive PR and events will be conducted to address their privacy concerns.

Product Requirement:

The med-drone will be autonomous, so there can be the risk that the drone might be vulnerable to the risk of being controlled by hackers. This risk will be addressed by employing built-in security and a virtual private network. Another risk would be the drone losing signals or the battery of the drone drops during delivery. For this risk, the return-to-home option will be added so as soon as such a situation occurs, the drone returns to its home location.

Resource Requirement:

The resource risk involved in our project can be a lack of staff, funding, and time. All these issues will be addressed by identifying the probability of a shortage of resources. All the resources will be optimized in different ways to ensure an efficient and productive outcome. For staff availability, planning of active succession will be performed to assure that if, for instance, an employee gets sick, there is a backup available. In absence of funding, cost-effective resources will be identified and utilized in such cases. Capacity planning will be done to assure that all resources are present for the project.

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Technical Infrastructure:

If the drone is unable to deliver beyond vision then it can threaten our system. Failure of the drone while delivering medicine can be a risk. The battery life of a drone is another factor that can pose a threat to our service. The risks will be mitigated using an autonomous drone manufactured by a team with technical expertise in this area. Return-to-home feature will be used to reduce the consequences of battery or failure issues.

Timing:

Project completion takes more time due to unanticipated changes in scope. The scope creep will be avoided by creating parameters of the project that are clear from the start. The project roadmap will be communicated to stakeholders from the start and upon their agreement project will be initiated. To mitigate the risk of the time crunch, a Gantt chart will be prepared with a clearly defined project schedule. Dependencies, project, and project lifecycle will be understood by all team members, which will also help allocate time to each task of the project.

External Consideration:

Delivery drones require licenses from the government for being operated which can be a challenge. There are some regulations for drone delivery services that will be followed by our drone technology. Our drone belongs to Class III of UAS systems so it needs a license and certificate for its operation. The exchange rate of Pakistan is unstable with high fluctuations. A contract with the element of exchange rate can be formed with the company from which parts will be imported.

Finance:

Lack of capital investment needed to purchase the drone, and pay salaries to staff to execute the drone technology and IT app. Financial forecasting will be performed to ensure all the finance are properly forecasted and will be closely monitored throughout the process.

Industry Requirements:

Lack of government regulations regarding drone usage in the health sector. This risk is external and the government can address this risk by devising regulations for the operation of drones in the healthcare sector. Some countries have used the drone for delivering

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COMPANY LOGO

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MTC Integration

vaccines and medicines during the period of COVID-19. So there is a high chance that our government will also develop regulations for its operation in this sector in the future.

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13.0 Project Assessment

(Input a check next to the overall project assessment.) This section qualifies the project teams overall assessment of the project in the building of this product. This assessment should encapsulate the project team's confidence level that the product/service description, aforementioned at the beginning of this document, is documented to its smallest detail and that the project can meet or exceed customer expectations in providing such product (given the current plan).

GREEN

YELLOW

RED

14. Formal Acceptance

Signature Disclaimer

By signing below, you confirm that you have read all the contents of the Product Description and any subsidiary plans and agree to the aforementioned details. By your signature, you endorse this project and commit to support the project team in its aim to achieve the stated goals and objectives. Your approval will be required if/when the project baseline changes

Ayesha Ahmad Khan

Project/Program Manager Signature

Project Sponsor Signature

Customer(s) Signature(s)

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